

Teachers' Protective Factors of Resilience Scale: Factorial Structure, Validity and Reliability Issues

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Abstract

In the last years, few measurement scales have been introduced to explore the concept of teachers' resilience. While these instruments have made valuable contributions to the field, they have been criticized for their failure to encompass several pivotal protective factors that literature has identified as central to teachers' resilience. In response to this weakness, the Teachers' Protective Factors of Resilience Scale (TPFRS, Daniilidou & Platsidou, 2022) was created which addresses these limitations by including an assessment of both personal and environmental protective factors that influence teachers' resilience. In this context, the present study was undertaken with the aim of testing the factorial structure, reliability and construct validity of the TPFRS, as well as the preferred protective factors of 964 primary and secondary school teachers who participated in the study. The results confirmed that the TPFRS is a robust and valid instrument for assessing the protective factors that underlie teachers' resilience, whereas the predominant protective factors were (1) Teachers' values and beliefs and (2) Emotional and behavioral competence. In conclusion, the TPFRS can be confidently recommended for use in subsequent research studies and interventions in the teaching profession.

Keywords: *Protective factors, resilience, teachers.*

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Introduction

Over the past decade, there has been a growing scientific interest in exploring teachers' resilience, leading to the creation of assessment tools tailored to this context. In this context, a limited yet notable set of instruments specifically designed for assessing teachers' resilience, such as the Multidimensional Teachers' Resilience Scale by Mansfield and Wosnitza (2015) and the Teachers' Resilience Scale by Daniilidou and Platsidou (2018) was emerged. At the same time, recent research findings (e.g., Botou et al., 2017; Daniilidou, 2023; Gu & Day, 2007; Yuan et al., 2013) have drawn attention

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to additional dimensions encompassing individual characteristics (e.g., humor, creativity, moral values) and environmental factors (e.g., family, friends, legislative framework). These factors, while recognized as contributors to teachers' resilience, remained unaddressed by the existing measurement scales. In light of the above considerations, the Teachers' Protective Factors of Resilience Scale (TPFRS, Daniilidou & Platsidou 2022) was designed to address the limitations observed in the existing scales. This new instrument comprehensively assesses the personal and the environmental protective factors underpinning teachers' resilience, which aid them in effectively confronting challenges in their profession and sustaining their commitment to their job. Since the TPFRS is a newly developed instrument, the present study was designed to verify its factor structure and confirm its convergent and discriminant validity, by administering it in a new sample of school teachers.

Protective factors of teachers' resilience

Teachers' resilience can be conceptually framed as a dynamic process characterized by the interplay between individual attributes and external environmental factors; collectively, these factors shape teachers' capacity to respond to and adapt in the face of the challenges inherent to their profession (Mansfield et al., 2012). Within this framework, teachers' resilience entails the intricate interplay of personal traits, like perseverance, optimism, and motivation, social aspects including relationships with peers and interactions with students, and physical/material features, such as school's infrastructure. These components collectively operate to address and mitigate the risk factors that arise within the educational milieu while optimizing available protective resources (Masten, 2014). The international literature has traditionally categorized the resilience protective factors into two broad dimensions: personal, or internal factors, and environmental, or external factors.

Personal Protective Factors

According to Mansfield and colleagues (Mansfield et al., 2016), teachers' personal protective factors of resilience consist of two pillars; (a) personal resources and motivation and (b) strategies for the utilization of personal resources.

Obviously, the first pillar pertains individual traits and characteristics. Although resilience is comprehended as a dynamic construct operating within a network of social interactions rather than a static personality trait (Luthar et al., 2000; Ungar, 2008), several studies have identified a relation between resilience and personality traits, as well as motivation (e.g., Peixoto et al., 2018; Skodol, 2010). Characteristics such as effectively managing adverse emotions and stress, displaying high emotional intelligence and a sense of humor, maintaining optimism, and exhibiting extraversion have been found to correlate with elevated levels of resilience among educators (see Mansfield et al., 2012 for an extended review). Furthermore, motivational factors such as deriving satisfaction from teaching and student interactions, a commitment to continual professional development, the process of making career decisions, and establishing attainable expectations and objectives (Mansfield et al., 2012; Tait, 2008) have been found to promote the preservation and/or enhancement of teachers' resilience.

The second pillar of the personal protective factors is defined by the strategies, which encompass the adaptive techniques and actions educators employ to restore balance when confronted with challenges (Perrez et al., 2005). Some researchers (e.g., Connor

& Davidson, 2003; Schwarze & Wosnitza, 2018) also include the coping strategies for managing stressful situations within the protective factors of resilience. Thus, a conceptual overlap exists between coping and resilience, implying that the strategies individuals employ to manage stressors can also play a role in determining their overall resilience levels. The strategies identified in the literature encompass the utilization of diverse teaching methods, problem-solving approaches, seeking assistance within their social networks, and the ability to disengage or emotionally distance themselves from stressful circumstances (Bowles & Arnup, 2016; Castro et al., 2010; Daniilidou, 2023; Mansfield et al., 2012).

Environmental Protective Factors

According to Ungar (2012), in order to better understand the concept of resilience, we must first explore the context in which it manifests. As a social construct (Ungar, 2008), resilience is influenced by environmental factors that are unique to each context. For example, the importance of supportive relationships in the work context is often cited as an important protective factor for teachers (e.g., Botou et al., 2017; Le Cornu, 2009; Mansfield et al., 2018; Schwarze & Wosnitza, 2018).

Gu (2018) suggested that the central components of teachers' professional lives revolve around three categories of relationships: the teacher-student relationship, interactions among teachers, and the association between teachers and school principals. Interactions between teachers and students, both within and outside the school environment, not only mitigate the stress encountered by teachers but also provide a compelling reason for their commitment to the teaching profession (Flores, 2006; Olsen & Anderson, 2007). Additionally, prior research has found that the positive relationships with colleagues are pivotal in fostering resilience (Papatraianou & Le Cornu, 2014), aiding teachers in navigating challenges by serving as a source of inspiration, hope, and morale boosters (Olsen & Anderson, 2007). Furthermore, the support and trust extended by school administrators have beneficial effects on teachers' motivation and resilience (Meister & Ahrens, 2011). In real-life settings, this can be observed when school administrators exert significant influence in fostering collegial relationships, maintain a balance in teacher interactions with students' parents, and provide support to novice teachers at the beginning of their careers (Gu, 2018).

In addition to the above, external factors outside the school context have been identified as contributing to the enhancement of teachers' resilience. Papatraianou and Le Cornu (2014) suggested that informal support networks, such as friends and family, exert an influence on teachers' resilience through providing emotional backing and creating an environment in which teachers can more freely express themselves. With their support, family members and friends help teachers in maintaining a healthy work-life balance by providing psychological and practical assistance and emotional release (Black & Lobo, 2008; Gu & Day, 2007). Lastly, although ongoing changes in educational policies and legislation are often mentioned by the teachers as sources of stress (e.g., Antoniou et al., 2023; Flores, 2018), it has been found that, in some cases, a comprehensive understanding of the legislative framework can be a factor of support and protection for the teachers (Daniilidou, 2023).

Instruments Assessing Teachers' Resilience

As mentioned earlier, in the international literature, only two tools have been developed to measure the protective factors of teachers' resilience. Both instruments present some limitations that will be discussed below.

The Multidimensional Teachers' Resilience Scale (MTRS) was developed by Mansfield and Wosnitza (2015) and assesses four dimensions of teachers' resilience: Professional resilience, Emotional competence, Social competence, and Motivation. This is a widely used scale and has been applied to international (e.g., Peixoto et al., 2018) as well as to Greek samples of teachers (e.g., Daniilidou et al., 2020; Platsidou & Daniilidou, 2021). However, in the Greek context, the MTRS exhibited an inconsistent factor structure (Daniilidou et al., 2020; Platsidou & Daniilidou, 2021). Specifically, it was found that the factorial structure of the scale deviated significantly from the original structure proposed by its creators. Furthermore, it is noteworthy that the MTRS primarily focuses on the assessment of internal resilience protective factors while it gives limited attention to environmental factors.

The Teachers' Resilience Scale (TRS), designed by Daniilidou and Platsidou (2018), was developed to comprehensively evaluate the personal as well as the environmental protective factors contributing to teachers' resilience. The TRS was derived from the combination of two existing scales which were addressed to the general adult population. Specifically, it incorporated the subscales of Personal competence and persistence, and Spiritual influences from the Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-Risc, Connor & Davidson, 2003) and the subscales of Family cohesion, and Social competence and peer support from the Resilience Scale for Adults (RSA, Hjemdal et al., 2005). Relative research has confirmed that the TRS is a valid and reliable instrument for assessing these protective resilience factors in both Greek teachers (Stavraki & Karagianni, 2020; Papazis et al., 2023) and teachers of other cultural contexts such as South Africa and the United States (Crompton et al., 2023), Iran (Namaziandost et al., 2022) and Poland (Boczkowska, 2021). However, it must be noted that the TRS, being a synthesis of two existing scales designed for general adult population, includes items that are phrased in a general manner and may not explicitly pertain to the teaching context where resilience is demonstrated. For example, statements like "I enjoy interacting with colleagues at my workplace" and "During challenging times, my family maintains a positive outlook for the future" do not focus on examining protective elements related to peer relationships and familial support within the challenges encountered specifically in the school environment.

To overcome the limitations of the two aforementioned scales, a new scale entitled Teachers' Protective Factors of Resilience Scale (TPFRS, Daniilidou & Platsidou, 2022) was developed. In particular, the TPFRS assesses a greater number of both personal and environmental resilience protective factors in the specific context of the teaching profession. The development of the TPFRS scale drew upon insights gained from previous scales, specifically those by Mansfield & Wosnitza (2015) and Daniilidou & Platsidou (2018), and from qualitative data obtained by Daniilidou (2018). These sources collectively contributed to the construction of the new scale, which takes into account an extended range of factors (compared to the previous instruments) that contribute to teachers' resilience and their ability to overcome the challenges they face in their professional environment.

Aims of the Study

As mentioned earlier, the TPFERS is a very recently developed measurement tool, which has been tested on a sample of Greek teachers (Daniilidou & Platsidou, 2022). In order to further investigate its psychometric properties, in the present study the TPFERS was administered in a new sample. Specifically, this study aimed: (a) to check the factorial structure of the TPFERS, (b) to check for its convergent and discriminant validity, and (c) to examine the dominant resilience protective factors used by teachers, according to their self-reports.

Materials and Methods

Sample

The sample consisted of 964 public school teachers (725 females, 239 males) coming from urban areas of Greece. Their age ranged from 23 to 65 years with a mean of 42.84 (SD = 10.94). Out of them, 595 (61.7%) teachers were employed in primary education and 369 (38.3%) in secondary education; 740 (76.6%) teachers were working in general education and 224 (23.2%) in special education. Their teaching experience ranged from 1 to 41 years with a mean of 15.53 (SD = 9.89).

Instruments

Teachers' protective resilience factors were assessed with the TPFERS (Daniilidou & Platsidou, 2022). It includes 29 items which assess six resilience protective factors: Teachers' values and beliefs (5 items, e.g., I draw strength from the feeling of completeness that teaching offers me), Emotional and behavioral competence (6 items, e.g., Classroom and teaching organization makes it easier for me to deal with the challenges), Physical well-being (3 items, e.g., I resort to physical exercise for relief), Relationships within the school environment, (6 items, e.g., I talk to the school principal asking for practical and psychological support), Relationships outside the school environment (5 items, e.g., I am relieved and unwind by talking to my family), and the Legislative framework of education (4 items, e.g., I am informed about what I am supposed to do based on the legal framework). The whole instrument is presented in the Appendix.

Participants are asked to give their responses on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 (never) to 5 (always). In the first testing of the TPFERS conducted in the study of Daniilidou and Platsidou (2022), the above inner factorial structure was confirmed and the internal reliability of the subscales was found to be adequate (Cronbach's α ranged from .68 to .88)

Procedure

A convenience sample of teachers was recruited and the study was conducted in March and April, 2021. Teachers participated voluntarily in the study and were not offered any additional incentives; they were assured that their participation would remain confidential and their responses would only be used for the purposes of this study. The Google Forms application was used to construct the electronic form of the instrument and it was distributed via email.

Results

Factorial Structure and Reliability of the TPFRS

First, the inner structure of the TPFRS was tested by applying a factor analysis with varimax rotation. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.87, and the Bartlett's test of sphericity was significant ($\chi^2(406) = 12264.28, p = .00$) indicating that factor analysis is suitable for all 29 items. The analysis revealed six factors which accounted for the 60.96% of the total variance.

To verify the above structure, a confirmatory factor analysis was performed on the 29 items. Results showed that the six-factor model fits the data well ($\chi^2/329 = 2.551, CFI = .933, GFI = .927, SRMR = .046, CI90\% = .044 - .049, RMSEA = .047$). The reliability of the six subscales was satisfactory (Cronbach's α ranged from .70 to .88). The factor loading matrix and the internal reliability indexes are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Factorial Structure and Reliability of the TPFRS

Items	Relationships outside the school environment	Emotional and behavioral competence	Teachers' Values and beliefs	Relationships within the school environment	Legislative framework	Physical wellbeing	E	R ²
I talk to someone close to me outside the workplace to vent	.832						.69	.42
It helps me sharing the problem and my feelings with my friends	.741						.55	.63
I am relieved and unwind by talking to my family	.778						.61	.56
I talk to my spouse/partner to relieve emotional pressure	.804						.65	.42
I seek advice from people close to me	.645						.42	.64
The knowledge I have gained from dealing with similar incidents in the past is useful when coping with similar situations		.602					.36	.37
I try through the discussion to explain my own point of view		.654					.31	.41
Taking an interest in the personal issues of my students and colleagues helps me to resolve conflicts that arise more easily		.618					.38	.40
Classroom and teaching organization makes it easier for me to deal with the challenges		.498					.25	.60
I recall strategies from the experience of previous years to deal with challenges me overcome similar challenges		.671					.45	.34

It is easier to handle difficult situations at school if I have anticipated them		.642					.41	.40
I draw strength from the feeling of completeness that teaching offers me			.746				.56	.33
I get strength from the sense of contribution I derive from my profession			.799				.64	.22
My love for students gives me the strength to go on			.665				.44	.38
I draw strength from interaction with students			.684				.47	.35
I am encouraged to think that the education I provide has value and impact on society			.703				.49	.26
There are people within the school context that I can turn to for help and support				.677			.46	.52
I seek advice from more experienced colleagues				.721			.28	.48
I discuss the problem with my colleagues				.711			.49	.39
I talk to the school principal asking for practical and psychological support				.666			.44	.54
I seek support and guidance from the education consultants				.538			.29	.52
I address to the school principal to solve the problem				.475			.23	.70
I refer to the relevant law regulating the situation					.782		.61	.41
I assert my rights based on the laws and the school regulation					.891		.79	.18
I rely on the knowledge of the regulation and laws on education to solve a problem					.719		.52	.41
I am informed about what I am supposed to do based on the legal framework					.691		.48	.54
I resort to physical exercise for relief						.653	.43	.62
A balanced diet can give me the energy I need to overcome the challenge more easily						.626	.39	.59
Being healthy and in a good physical condition can have a positive impact on the way I react						.697	.49	.49
Cronbach's α	.85	.79	.88	.76	.82	.70		

Convergent and discriminant validity of the TPFRS

The second aim of the study was to evaluate the convergent validity and the discriminant validity of the new scale. Convergent validity, defined as the ability of the scale to accurately measure a particular characteristic, can be assessed employing various criteria (Chin & Yao, 2014). In this study, it was assessed following the Fornell-Larcker (1981) criterion, a widely utilized method for determining the extent of shared variance among latent variables within a model.

In particular, we assessed the convergent validity of the measurement model using two key metrics: the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and the Composite Reliability (CR). More explicitly, AVE quantifies the proportion of variance captured by a construct relative to the variance attributed to measurement error. AVE values exceeding 0.7 are indicative of excellent convergent validity, while values at the 0.5 level are considered acceptable. CR is considered a more robust measure of reliability compared to Cronbach's Alpha, with a CR value of 0.7 or higher being acceptable. For achieving convergent validity, AVE is required to equal or exceed 0.50 and remain lower than CR, as reported by Hair et al. (2010). Our results (presented in Table 2), indicate that both AVE and CR meet these criteria, thus providing substantial support for the convergent validity of the TPFRS.

Discriminant validity is also defined in a number of ways in the existing literature and a variety of ways is proposed for its evaluation (Rönkkö et al., 2022). In the present study, discriminant validity was evaluated by assessing the degree to which the factors within the scale are distinct and not inter-correlated. Discriminant validity is achieved when AVE exceeds both the Maximum Shared Squared Variance (MSV) and the Average Shared Squared Variance (ASV), as suggested by Hair et al. (2010). As shown in Table 2, for all factors examined, AVE values exceeded both MSV and ASV values, thus establishing the discriminant validity of the TPFRS.

Table 2. Convergent and Discriminant Validity of the TPFRS

Factors	CR	AVE	MSV	ASV
Physical well-being	.78	.55	.10	.06
Teachers' values and beliefs	.87	.57	.20	.10
Emotional and behavioral competence	.82	.51	.20	.12
Relationships within the school environment	.82	.53	.18	.11
Relationships outside the school context	.90	.65	.10	.05
Legislative framework	.85	.60	.18	.10

Note: CR = Composite Reliability, AVE = Average Variance Extracted, MSV = Maximum Shared Variance, ASV = Average Shared Variance

Teachers' Dominant Protective Factors of Resilience

The final aim of the study was to investigate the dominant protective factors contributing to resilience as revealed by teachers' responses. The findings presented in Table 3 reveal that teachers prioritize personal protective factors as paramount to maintaining and/or enhancing their resilience.

Table 3. Means and Standard Deviations of Teachers' Protective Resilience Factors

	Mean	SD
Teachers' values and beliefs	4.22	.63
Emotional and behavioral competence	4.15	.57
Legislative framework	3.78	.80
Physical wellbeing	3.65	.82
Relationships within school environment	3.50	.72
Relationships outside school environment	3.49	.96

Note: Responses were given in a 5-point Likert scale

Discussion

The present study was carried out to check the factor structure and the psychometric properties of the TPFRS, a newly developed instrument for assessing the protective factors of teachers' resilience. After conducting a comprehensive series of analyses, as reported previously, it was found that the TPFRS demonstrates a consistent factor structure and exhibits satisfactory convergent and discriminant validity.

In particular, the TPFRS evaluates six protective factors, comprising three internal/personal factors (Values and beliefs, Emotional and behavioral competence, and Physical well-being) and three external/environmental factors (Relationships within the school context, Relationships outside the school context, and Legislative framework). It is worth noting that this number exceeds the number of the factors assessed by other relative instruments. Researchers like Ungar (2011) and Lerner (2006) have emphasized the importance of examining the interplay between individuals and their environment when exploring development of resilience. Aligned to the above, apart from the personal factors typically considered in existing instruments, the TPFRS extends its scope to encompass protective factors pertained to the social and ecological dimensions of resilience. Specifically, in terms of the Bronfenbrenner's (1977) ecological model, the TPFRS assesses interactions at both the microsystem (e.g., relationships with colleagues and students) and the mesosystem (e.g., interactions with the school principal), as well as interactions at the macrosystem (e.g., legislative framework) of teachers' working life. It is worth noting that the TRPFS is the only scale in the relevant international literature that comprehensively assesses a wider range of protective factors of resilience and has been created specifically for teachers. Finally, this study aimed to explore which factors are of paramount importance for enhancing teachers' resilience in their workplace, as perceived by them. It was found that the two most preferred protective factors were Teachers' values and beliefs and Emotional and behavioral competence.

The Teachers' values and beliefs subscale pertains to teachers' perceptions of their profession, stemming from intrinsic and altruistic motivations that sustain their commitment and dedication to their job. Empirical research has consistently demonstrated that extrinsic motivators, such as monetary rewards and career advancement opportunities, do not exert as much influence on teachers as a profound sense of purpose does (Klaeijssen et al., 2018; Mansfield et al., 2016). On an individual level, teachers' values and passion for their job is linked to a robust sense of purpose, well-defined professional objectives, resilience, optimism, and heightened motivation (Barni et al., 2019; Gu & Day, 2007). Within the school context, when teachers' moral values and sense of purpose are integral components of school ethos, or when there is a shared sense of mission among all school stakeholders, the likelihood of achieving high goals through collaborative efforts is greatly enhanced.

The Emotional and behavioral competence subscale primarily encompasses teachers' proficiency in organization, their capacity for empathy, and their utilization of prior professional experience. Skillful organization and meticulous planning of the teaching processes can contribute to more effective crisis management within the school setting (Hong, 2012). As underscored by Parker and Martin (2009), organization and planning rank among the strategies for meeting challenges and can predict increased levels of performance, well-being, and engagement. Furthermore, actively listening to the concerns of others and demonstrating empathy can be a catalyst for building

supportive relationships and skillfully addressing the daily challenges teachers face (Daniilidou, 2023; Huang et al., 2020). Finally, the process of recollection, encompassing strategies that have yielded favorable outcomes in the past, and reflecting on those that did not perform as anticipated contributes to continual learning. This learning process aids in managing issues, mitigating the impact of stressful circumstances and facilitating decision-making, ultimately enabling teachers to manage risky situations more effectively (Daniilidou, 2023; Djalante & Thomalla, 2011).

It is worth noting that, according to their self-reports, teachers resort mainly to the use of internal rather than external protective factors in order to enhance their resilience. Of the latter, the most important is the legislative framework. Apparently, although it looks tedious to delve into laws and regulations, it proves to be a very important source of strengthening resilience and it constitutes a protective factor that teachers value, recognize and use.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the development of a new scale assessing the protective factors of teachers' resilience marks a significant advancement in understanding the complex interplay between individual characteristics and environmental influences in fostering resilience within the educational sector and sheds light on the specific factors that contribute to teachers' ability to withstand and thrive amidst the challenges of their profession. By identifying and measuring these protective factors, our research opens avenues for targeted interventions that can enhance resilience across various professions, particularly those characterized by high stress and burnout rates. Furthermore, this scale sets the stage for future research to explore the universality of these protective factors across different cultural contexts and professional settings, potentially leading to the development of universally applicable resilience-building strategies. As we move forward, it is imperative that subsequent studies build upon this foundation, exploring the dynamic nature of resilience and its impact on individual and organizational outcomes in diverse contexts.

Future Research

Based on all of the above, it appears that the TPFERS can be a valid and reliable tool for assessing the factors that facilitate teachers' resilience. Our future goal is to test the TPFERS in international samples to examine its factorial structure and validity in different cultural and educational settings.

Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix

	When I face challenges at the school environment....	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
1	I draw strength from the feeling of completeness that teaching offers me	1	2	3	4	5
2	I am relieved and unwind by talking to my family	1	2	3	4	5
3	I am informed about what I am supposed to do based on the legal framework	1	2	3	4	5
4	I recall strategies from the experience of previous years to deal with challenges	1	2	3	4	5
5	I get strength from the sense of contribution I derive from my profession	1	2	3	4	5
6	I resort to physical exercise for relief	1	2	3	4	5
7	I try through the discussion to explain my own point of view	1	2	3	4	5
8	I talk to someone close to me outside the workplace to vent	1	2	3	4	5
9	I talk to the school principal asking for practical and psychological support	1	2	3	4	5
10	I refer to the relevant law regulating the situation	1	2	3	4	5
11	The knowledge I have gained from dealing with similar incidents in the past is useful when coping with similar situations	1	2	3	4	5
12	My love for students gives me the strength to go on	1	2	3	4	5
13	I discuss the problem with my colleagues	1	2	3	4	5
14	A balanced diet can give me the energy I need to overcome the challenge more easily	1	2	3	4	5
15	I assert my rights based on the laws and the school regulation	1	2	3	4	5
16	I draw strength from interaction with students	1	2	3	4	5
17	I talk to my spouse/partner to relieve emotional pressure	1	2	3	4	5
18	Classroom and teaching organization makes it easier for me to deal with the challenges	1	2	3	4	5
19	I seek support and guidance from the education consultants	1	2	3	4	5
20	I seek advice from more experienced colleagues	1	2	3	4	5
21	I rely on the knowledge of the regulation and laws on education to solve a problem	1	2	3	4	5
22	It helps me sharing the problem and my feelings with my friends	1	2	3	4	5
23	There are people within the school context that I can turn to for help and support	1	2	3	4	5

24	I am encouraged to think that the education I provide has value and impact on society	1	2	3	4	5
25	Being healthy and in a good physical condition can have a positive impact on the way I react	1	2	3	4	5
26	Taking an interest in the personal issues of my students and colleagues helps me to resolve conflicts that arise more easily	1	2	3	4	5
27	I seek advice from people close to me	1	2	3	4	5
28	I address to the school principal to solve the problem	1	2	3	4	5
29	It is easier to handle difficult situations at school if I have anticipated them	1	2	3	4	5

